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SAFEGUARD POLICY AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF DESIGN IN THE NEWLY INDUSTRIALIZING COUNTRIES (NICS) - THE CASE OF TAIWAN HOUSEHOLD APPLIANCE INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

Governments of newly industrializing countries (NICs) after the Second World War have often been keenly involved in market intervention, adopting protectionist policies in order to foster local infant industries and provide a breeding ground for the development of industrial design. The household appliance industry in Taiwan is a typical case. As such, this study followed the historical evolution of Taiwan's household appliance industry and reviewed the establishment of design divisions in local household appliance manufacturers, including Tatung Co. and Sampo Co. Through investigating historical documents and interviewing senior personnel in the industry, this study explore how household appliance companies respond to domestic consumer characteristics and the pressure of international economic liberalization in the mid-1980s with the execution of industrial policies and technical support from foreign capital.

This study placed industrial design within the framework of the environmental changes of industries and the growth of enterprises, reviewing their developmental journeys and clarifying the characteristics of industrial design in Taiwan's household appliance industry. This study breaks through existing writings on design history that only focus on designers and design works. The strategic role played by the design division in corporate expansion also provides inspiration for the other industries.

Keywords: Design history, Taiwan's economic development, Household appliance industry.

INTRODUCTION

RESEARCH BACKGROUND: THE EMERGENCE OF TAIWAN'S HOUSEHOLD APPLIANCE INDUSTRY

Household appliances are electrical home appliances, which can often be categorized into white goods and brown goods. White goods refer to household electrical goods, including refrigerators, washing machines, microwaves and dishwashers, whereas brown goods are electronic devices, such as televisions, stereos and audio-visual equipment. Household appliances are often regarded as a symbol of social progress, bearing witness to material transformation during the process of modernization.

Because household appliances, such as gas stoves and refrigerators, use energy, they create huge business opportunities for energy companies. Electric utility companies are often important promoters of the innovation and sales of household appliances. All types of household appliances, from heating equipment to cooking appliances, such as kettles, toasters, dish washers, washing machines and vacuum cleaners, are invented one by one based on the purpose of expanding the domestic consumption of electricity and maximizing the load factors of electric utility companies (Forty, 1986). Electric utility companies advocate and encourage the use of electricity; they also work with electrical engineers to actively innovate new household appliances, which contribute to the electrification of households and rural villages. As a result, the ratios of industrial and domestic electrical consumptions have gone in opposite directions, which become the norm for the development of electrical utilities in various countries. During this historical process, one of the great successes of using styling as advertising, and one that gave a spur to the growth of the American industrial design profession, was 'streamlining' (Dormer, 1990). As such, electric utility companies, the household appliance industry, and industrial design became mutual driving forces in the historical development process. However, an examination of Taiwan's experience shows that this process was full of difficulties.

In 1950, Taiwan's first power plant, the Taipei First Power Plant, started operating, and the general public was allowed to apply for electricity. Electric lights were the first electrical appliances to go into Taiwanese households. However, due to developmental delays of the Sun Moon Lake Power Plant, plus the eruption of the Second World War, domestic consumption capacity was low; therefore, the electrification of households was not realized. In 1950 the Korean War erupted, and US aid flooded in. Taiwan used this opportunity to launch its industrialization, and the large-scale electrification of the island was pushed forward in the mid-1950s by the government. Prior to this, because the use of electrical energy was uncommon, plus the needs of society came last under the military regime, the government regarded household appliances as luxury goods. In 1965, the government imposed higher

commodity taxes on household appliances and cosmetics, and also checked the amounts of energy used by household appliances through the Taiwan Power Company. It called upon the general public to be thrifty with electricity consumption. Facing the lack of direct subsidies from electric utility companies, household appliance manufacturers had to find new ways to develop commodity sources by themselves.

In the 1930s, Taiwanese and Japanese businessmen were assembling and selling radios and gramophones in Taiwan. After the Second World War, local businessmen, who were familiar with the production and sales of household appliances during the Japanese colonization period, started to expand their businesses one by one. In 1946, Chien-chuan Hong established the Chien Long Trading House, specializing in a set of businesses, including the trading of electrical materials and the installation and maintenance of electrical appliances. In 1949, Shi-Chu Lee, Chuan-Liu Chang and Yun-lian Liao established a joint venture named Central Wireless Electric. In 1956, Mao-Bang Chen established the Ton Cheng Tang Company, which manufactured radio components. Through several changes, the above three companies later on became Panasonic Taiwan Co., Ltd., Sanyo Electric Taiwan Co., Ltd., and the Sampo Corporation. Other similar household appliance entrepreneurs included Ke-chun Lee and Chao-Pei Liu, who established the Kolin Group in 1963, which specialized in the manufacturing of black-and-white televisions.

In addition, Ting-shen Lin, the son of the founder of Tatung Iron Works Shang-Chi Lin, succeeded the company that was established in 1939; he then transformed this steel and machinery manufacturing company into household appliance production. He considered himself to be a national industrial entrepreneur, and rapidly expanded his enterprise during the 1960s. The turnovers of Tatung topped all private enterprises at the time. Teco Electric & Machinery Co., Ltd. was founded in 1956, which mainly manufactured motors; in 1959 it began to develop electric fans, entering the industry of household appliances.

After the year 1962, influenced by factors including the broadcasting of television channels and the rise of national income, consumer demands for household appliances suddenly appeared, which attracted foreign capital, mainly from Japan, to invest and undergo technical cooperation. After the 1960s, under the assistance of Japanese trading companies, large household and machinery companies from Japan started to develop the market in Taiwan, looking for corporate partners through networks built during the colonization period. The Panasonic Group was the first Japanese company to establish a Taiwanese branch (Panasonic Taiwan Co., Ltd.) in 1962, which was followed by Sanyo Electric Co., Ltd. and other large Japanese electric and machinery manufacturers, such as Toshiba, Mitsubishi and Hitachi, which all formed joint

ventures with local enterprises (as shown in Table 1) under the Taiwanese government's policy of attracting foreign capital (Lee & Huang, 1993) and carrying out technical cooperation. In the beginning, the cooperation started with Japanese companies providing equipment and importing materials and semi-finished products from Japan, which were assembled by joint ventures in Taiwan and then sold in local markets.

Table 1. Investments of Japanese electrical companies in Taiwan

Time (Year/Month)	Local Company	Partner	Japanese share
1962/10	Panasonic Taiwan	Panasonic Group	56 %
1962/11	Tatung	Toshiba	5%
1963/3	Sanyo Taiwan	Sanyo Sanyo Trading	49 %
1965/4	Hitachi Taiwan	Hitachi	61.5 %
1968/7	TFC	Toshiba Toshiba Litec	4.81 % 3.28 %
1971/2	Sampo	Sharp	8.25 %
1987/5	Taisei	Fujitsu General	66.9 %
1988/4	Denso Taiwan	Denso Japan	80 %
1991/2	Toshiba Compressor	Toshiba	67 %

Source: Lee & Huang, 1993.

In the early days, household appliances were very expensive. The cost of an electric fan equaled 1 tael (37.5 grams) of gold; thus, consumers were mainly from the middle and upper classes. During the period between 1963 and 1972, Taiwan's average economic growth exceeded 10%, creating the world-renowned 'economic miracle', which drove the vigorous purchasing capacities of the Taiwanese people. Televisions, refrigerators and other products began to enter the daily lives of Taiwanese people; the Sampo Napoleon television, the Sanyo Happy Mum washing machine, and Tatung rice cookers were well known at that time. Accompanying the electrification of Taiwanese households, these types of household appliances became the rising stars for household necessities and domestic markets, establishing the scale of the household appliance industry.

THE CONCEIVING OF HOUSEHOLD APPLIANCE DESIGN

Accompanying the emergence of Taiwan's household appliance markets, companies changed their business models from importing to local production, and their organizational scale gradually became complete; enterprises started to adopt research and development (R&D), setting up industrial design divisions one by one. The reason why the household appliance industry and industrial design collaborated with each other earlier than other industries might be rooted in the fact that Taiwan's household appliance industry started

earlier than other industries, and it better fitted the rapidly changing social needs caused by economic growth. However, the question of whether Taiwanese household appliance manufacturers needed to actively innovate and design new products could be examined under the bigger environment of the whole market. On the one hand, due to the specific conditions and user needs of the Taiwanese market, both Japanese parent companies and Taiwanese joint ventures all needed to develop new products of different specifications. For example, washing machines in Taiwan were often placed on the balcony, so the painted steel shell was replaced with Fiber-reinforced plastic (FRP).

On the other hand, the Taiwanese government set tariff barriers; policies and tax structures allowed foreign techniques and key components to be imported, whereas finished products were not easily imported. Excluding competition from foreign companies, Taiwanese household appliance manufacturers could easily dominate local markets. In addition, based on tax incentives, companies with tax preferences could export products with lower prices to the global market and earn foreign exchange. As there was no urgent need for industrial development, industrial design developed slowly and with minimum progress in the early stages. In the 1970s the mechanism of this division became more and more mature day by day.

As Table 1 shows, most Taiwanese household appliance manufacturers had foreign stakes; according to whether foreign capital exceeded half of the total equity, companies could be categorized into local companies and foreign joint ventures. Generally speaking, local companies adopted industrial design earlier and had continuous developments, whereas foreign joint ventures were comparatively not so active. Although foreign joint ventures brought in human resources and technology expansion that generated 'spillover effect' for the locale, the development of design divisions were often decided by the parent companies regarding Taiwan's position within global production networks. As this had to do with the marketing strategies of foreign capital, it was therefore full of uncertainty. Overall, foreign joint ventures had different innovative densities over different periods in different industries; the international economic factors involved were very complicated.

Most founders of Taiwanese household appliance companies either had business contacts with the Japanese during the Japanese colonization period or had been hired by the Japanese. The post-war system and environment indirectly urged Taiwan's household appliance industry to resume its connections with Japan before WWII, both as sales agents and as joint ventures. Taiwanese companies chose Japanese enterprises as business partners because the Taiwanese people were familiar with and yearned for the Japanese life style during the colonization period. However, companies with

Japanese capital in Taiwan mainly focused on manufacturing, and were not interested in innovative activities (Liu, 2002). According to the 'flying geese model' raised by the Japanese scholar Akamatsu Kaname, and Vernon's product life cycle theory (1966) that analyzed American companies' investment strategies through the viewpoints of international investment and trade, the global shifts of multinational corporations are fast and ruthless. As such, this study chose large local household appliance manufacturers, including Tatung and Sampo, as the analytical scope, analyzing the growing trajectory of their R&D divisions and design operations.

METHODOLOGY

Traditional design history often focuses on the lives and declarations of designers, linking these with the styles of their design works; pays little attention to the role played by corporations during the production process. However, the historian Walker (1989) once suggested an analogy: compared with the emphasis on patronage, which has been an important subject within the discipline of art history, design history should shift the emphasis to the histories of enterprises and companies that may employ teams of in-house designers and/or a succession of freelance, consultant designers. Therefore, the design profile and corporate image are not individual achievements but collective ones that evolve and change over time. As such, texts of design history generally blend some social and economic history with the history of trade, business, management, marketing, invention and product innovations.

The design historian Adrian Forty further reflected on the relationship between designers and their corporations. Forty doubted whether there are corresponding relationships between designers' ideas and their works. Although designs come up with different ideas, it is the entrepreneur and not the designer who chooses which to put into production (Forty, 1986). In a capitalist society, design is not done to give expression to the designer's creativity and imagination, but rather to make products that are salable and profitable (Forty, 1986). According to this, research on design history must place designers' creativity under the background of enterprises' pursuit of profits when doing analysis; the role played by design in economic development thus becomes an important issue of design history. Peter Dormer combined corporate history to discuss how designers undertook design activities during the process of corporate revitalization after WWII. Researches such as that done by John Heskett (1989) on Philips' design strategies and Sibylle Kicherer (1990) on Olivetti's design processes are both classics of design management and important literature of design history (Dormer, 1993). However, British design historian Penny Sparke (1987) stated that there is a danger in emphasizing the social, economic, political, and ideological context at the

expense of design's own influential role; in the hands of responsible manufacturers, designers, critics, and theorists, design can act as a powerful agent of change.

Summarizing the above-mentioned discussions, recent research on design history has started the endeavor to surpass the status quo of merely focusing on designers and their works, and displays the blending with corporate/industrial development histories. For instance, de Rijk (2009) used the example of the design and marketing of Dutch electrical household goods to show how American culture influenced its design development during 1930 and 1945. In addition to culture, policy also influences the development of design. For instance, when the Korean War erupted in 1950, the United States effectively sealed off Hong Kong's trade with the People's Republic of China; thereafter, the design development of Hong Kong lost its advantage in the Pearl River Delta. The quality of indigenous Hong Kong Chinese design rapidly declined, and the modernization process of traditional Chinese aesthetics lost its edge, as it was forced to be subordinate to the dominance of US design (Turner, 1989). From the 1970s, although Papanek and Bonsiepe first conveyed their design ideas for third world societies, the idea they advocated did not really work because they lacked political dimensions in their implementation. Therefore Amin (2004) sought to offer a new perspective to implement the idea of design as a solution for third world societies by looking at the interweaving of design and politics. These studies have broadened issues in traditional research of design history, which include how national cultural identities and international political economies influence regional industrial environments and the development of design, as well as the complicated social structures in the third world. However, the above-mentioned research papers have all treated regional/national design as a whole, and have not dealt with the subtle differences of individual industries and companies, not to mention an in depth examination of the context of development from design divisions of corporations.

This problem was pointed out by Er (1997) in an attempt to establish the developmental model of industrial design in NICs: 'In particular, empirical studies at firm and industry levels are vital, since industrial design activity does not occur in a vacuum but within the corporate structure of a firm'.

From this viewpoint of the historical context of post-war Taiwan, the development of industries has local specifications. In post-war developing countries, the government often actively intervenes in industrial development, which is called 'the developmental state' (Castells, 2001) [1]. In the 1960s, under the wave of the new international division of labor, foreign capital flooded into Taiwan. The industries that foreign capital invested in were concentrated in electronics, chemicals, machinery, and metal industries; as for cases of technological

corporation brought by foreign capital, the trend also showed the same pattern (Sumiya, Liu, & Tu, 1993; Taniura, 1992). Taiwan's electronics industry is a new industry developed almost entirely by foreign investment, combining intensive labor and the import and export of materials, components and products, integrated into the system of the international division of labor.

As such, this study analyzed the establishment, the channels of learning design and techniques, and the adjustment of trading regulations of post-war Taiwanese household appliance companies, to add clarity to the intricate relationships among government (policies on industries), foreign capital (technology transfer), and local companies (learning of technologies). The analytical framework is shown in Figure 1. This helps to understand how industrial design has grown from the realities of the industry in Taiwan, and to understand how this process forms the characteristics of industrial design in Taiwan.

Figure 1. Analytical framework

RESEARCH METHOD

This study explored data from different sets of literature and documents, as well as interviews with corporate personnel. Detailed research methods are further stated as follows.

1. Data collection

Data sources included: 1) newspaper clippings; 2) magazines and newspapers, including *Industrial Design Journal*, *Industrial Design and Packing Quarterly*, *Industrial Design Report*, and *Chinese Industrial Design Magazine*; 3) historical documents, including archives and the Report on the Plan for Enhancing Industrial Design Abilities from Academic Sinica; and 4) statistics data.

2. Interviews with personnel from the industry

The publishers of existing data were mostly out of institutes, such as the China Productivity Center (CPC), the Taiwan External Trade Development Council (TAITRA), and the China Industrial Designers Association (CIDA). These bodies

report and write from the perspective of promoting design; therefore, aside from the problem that the main themes of their articles may not fit the research questions of this study. Interviews not only confirmed the contents of these data and supplemented the insufficient parts; the researcher could also actively raised questions through the interviews.

This study chose interviewees based on the aforementioned contexts; participants were introduced through acquaintances in order to gain trust, and consent was obtained before conducting interviews. The interviewees were mainly employees of prestigious consumer appliance manufacturers who entered the company during the early period of the establishment of the design division.

All of the interviews were conducted by the researcher in person, in order to minimize uncertainties. Most participants were interviewed once, with interviews lasting about two hours each, and with interview guidelines sent to the participants beforehand. At least two participants were interviewed from the representative companies. The interview could be compared with existing documentation to form triangulation, so as to improve the research quality.

SLOW START - CONCEIVING THE EMBRYO OF THE DESIGN DIVISION

THE FIRST MOVER OF THE HOUSEHOLD APPLIANCE INDUSTRY - TATUNG CO.

Among all the Taiwanese companies who have contacts with foreign capital, Tatung is the one that has the business vision for a modern corporation, and therefore has a higher degree of acceptance of industrial design. Ever since the 1960s, Tatung has nurtured design talents. In addition to selecting outstanding crew members to work in the design division of Toshiba and to study in the department of design at Chiba University in Japan, representatives were sent to a series of industrial design summer courses held by the CPC and the TAITRA. In 1966, the Tatung Institute of Technology started recruitment for its newly established department of industrial design, systematically training design talents for the company, and Kyuushichi Miyajima was invited to give lectures at both the institute and the company from 1966 to 1967. At the same time, the design division at Toshiba sent personnel to give lectures on industrial design at the Tatung Institute of Technology, and Tatung Co. also sent designers to Japan to do short-term training, and form intensive interchanges. Katsuhei Toyoguchi and Kyochi Toyoguchi [2] became design advisors for Tatung Co. from the late 1960s. In the late 1970s, Tatung Co. sent ten designers to study abroad in world-renowned universities, which showed the company paid much attention to industrial design. After this training and education, designers who returned home could incorporate the strong points of each country's

design, and then develop methods that most suited local circumstances.

In 1971, based on long-term mutual exchanges with Toshiba, and as suggested by Kyochi Toyoguchi, Ting-shen Ling instructed Yuan-zin Zheng to set up a design division. In the beginning there were only nine people, but the division grew larger and larger after incorporating designers from each division (as shown in Figure 2). Three years later the division expanded, and five groups were set up under this division: 1) planning; 2) product development; 3) electrical household goods; 4) small electrical appliances; and 5) air conditioners. After the China Television Co. and the Chinese Television System started broadcasting, market demands for televisions escalated, and the focus of the design division thus shifted from household goods to video and audio equipment.

The design division innovated more than 300 products per year, fulfilling Ting-shen Lin's reliance on design. After design departments initially separated from each division were centralized in one independent division, the plant manager had to negotiate through conferences and could not give commands directly; this parallel relationship of communication raised the position of industrial design within the corporation. After design gained a certain degree of dominance in the process of product development, the relation to production, which used to be of least importance, was re-adjusted. Before Yuan-zin Zheng stepped down in 1979, the scale of the design division had reached 100 members. In addition to learning from the experiences of Japanese design experts, the division had frequent mutual exchanges with foreign companies' design divisions because of Tatung's businesses abroad and Zheng's overseas study in Germany. The design division at Tatung could be said to be highly globalized, and there were also designers from Germany, US and Japan who joined Tatung. Despite its reliance on Toshiba's supply of key components, industrial design at Tatung could compete with Toshiba and was at no rate inferior.

Even so, outstanding industrial design abilities did not alter Taiwan's dependence on technology imports from Japanese companies. For example, televisions that started to make hot sales in the late 1960s were assembled by engineers who had gone to Japan to learn the internal mechanical configuration from Toshiba. What Toshiba transferred to Tatung were mostly outdated models that had already been on the Japanese market for two to three years. During the technology transfer process, the leading production party decides the dominant-subordinate relationship within the process of product development: engineering institutions come first, and appearance and style design comes after (interviewee TB).

Figure 1: Greeting card designed and printed by the design division of Tatung, which shows the department had reached a certain scale.

Source: Zheng, 1977.

Every time when Japan launched a new product, it often became popular and was in great demand throughout Taiwan. The market trend that followed Japanese popular products made companies notice that those who could manufacture copies of Japanese products could earn huge profits (interviewees SA and TA). Since competitors within the island also obtained technological sources from Japanese corporations, in order to snatch business opportunities, the time for developing a new product was often minimized; conflicts often unavoidably happened between the mechanical and the design division, and mechanical constraint was often the pre-condition of style design.

BOTTOM-UP - SAMPO CO.

Sampo Corporation, another large local consumer appliance manufacturer, is a competitor of Tatung in the domestic market. It started to employ industrial design personnel in 1960. At that time there were about 20 designers, and the annual budget invested in innovation was as high as 4%. Although the owner of the corporation paid great attention to design, the individual departments did not care about it, and mocked designers as beautifying staff (interviewee SE). In 1966, the electronics department, located in Banchio city (which mainly manufactured televisions), already had an early model of design division, called 'the first development division', that was in charge of all product design within the corporation. In 1973, the launch of the Sampo fixed-cabinet television, named Napoleon, became a classic during that period that brought huge profits for the corporation (interviewee SB); the number of crewmembers in the television design division reached 30 at one point.

Compared with the centralization of Tatung's design division in the 1970s, Sampo's design divisions were distributed into individual plants due to the company's adopting of a profit-centered

organizational model. After the household appliance department at Linkou plant (manufacturing telephone and electrical household goods) officially went into operation in 1978, design divisions were incorporated into each department, thereby demoting the organizational level of design units, whose subordinate role in development projects for new products experienced great difficulties. After the design staff's continuous self-enriching of technical knowledge, plus the reinforcement of communication and active recommendations, the design units at Linkou and Tucheng were raised to a 'division' level in 1988 and 1989, respectively. In 1990, design divisions in three plants were further raised to the 'department' level, finally managing to be on an equal footing with other technical innovation departments (Lee, 1996). Sampo's understanding towards industrial design began in the 1960s; however, it took 20 years for the design department to climb from a bottom unit to a top unit.

In addition to technical issues, design staff also needed to face the marketing department's review under the market-oriented situation. In 1984, the design department at Sampo Co. officially started interchanges with that at Sharp Co. Around the year 1984, the design department at Sampo started to make contact with the design division of the Sharp Corporation in Japan, holding design exchange activities annually. The Japanese corporation provided professional experience about technology, organization, design trends, and so on, according to Sampo's demands, and charged high-priced advisory fees. Those activities were later suspended due to their inefficiencies, plus the household appliance industry was in recession and required cost reductions, as well as the frequent changes of staff that made it difficult for imported technologies to adhere to the enterprise for long.

In 1983, Sampo Co. established its research institute, which was in charge of the research and development of middle-and-long-term products. In the late 1980s, Sampo had matured to a stage where it could operate systematic product development processes across each department, could undertake in-depth independent thinking and planning, could reinforce leadership skills, and could inspire creativity regarding organizational functions, business types, corporate targets, and the developmental vision of the industrial design department in order to improve performance. Industrial design grew with the corporation; through the refining and baptism of the reality, it was transformed from an artist that beautifies product styles to an engineer and sales person with strong engineering knowledge and marketing abilities, which more sharply reflected market trends. After the 1990s, the design department at Sampo was able to make design policies independently, planning its own product identity system, and improving on the original product models from Japan.

LEARNING DESIGN THROUGH COUNTERFEITING

Tatung and Sampo not only carried out educational interchanges with their technical cooperation parent companies, they also undertook education and training inside the corporation. Tatung's design division held a weekly 'academic conference on industrial design', gathering industrial-design-related staff from both the university and the company. In addition to in-house designers, foreign designers and advisors were also included, as well as engineers who were innovating new models at that time. Each conference had a main theme that brought in new ideas, technologies and statistics. In addition, every summer, representatives from the Nippon Toyoguchi Design Institute were invited to hold training courses. The nurturing and training of industrial designers at Tatung was quite thorough. It not only covered style design and chromatics, but also included presentation drawings, mould graphics, explosive drawings, tables of components, etc, as well as cost analysis of materials and hints about manufacturing technologies, for the reference of the purchasing staff. Designers needed to participate in planning and simulated marketing from the beginning. In contrast with Tatung, a designer of Sampo Co. named Shen-shiong Chen, at the early stage of Sampo's establishment, after finishing his internship from Sharp in Japan, gathered colleagues from the design department to carry out unofficial learning activities.

Kyuushichi Miyajima assisted the department of industrial design at Tatung Institute of Technology to plan the curriculum at its early stages, and also lectured in the company. While he was lecturing industrial design in Tatung Co., he made the following metaphor: 'Industrial design is very simple, it's like dressing a person' (interviewee TB). Although looking back now it is not necessarily true, it was easier for people to understand during that time, when most people knew very little about industrial design. This also pointed out there was a clear distinction between mechanism and design.

Because key components were mostly provided by Japanese companies, when Tatung Co. received better mechanical components, design could better be brought into full play; the bigger the mechanical parts, the bulkier the finished design product (interviewee SA). Therefore, the problem had to be overcome and revised by the outer style, for example: the design of TV cases often adopted multi-layered 3D sculpting to amend the clear gap between the monitor that used a curved picture tube and the mask. Not until the flat square (FS) picture tube was invented, did the slim design replace the previous multi-groove design. The style design of televisions was generally influenced by Japanese popular style. The whole appearance design presented the changing trends from foot-stand to fixed-cabinet, and then to desktop models; the materials of the outer cases changed from wooden to plastic, and the colors from pine effects to black.

As for refrigerators, because most components and moulds were from Japan, Taiwanese household manufacturers had to use them as the base from which to make changes to the outer shell, interior arrangement and the handle; the designs carried out were mostly limited to plates, graphics, and corrugated paper packaging. In 1986, designers at Sampo suggested a design proposal about a refrigerator with no handle, which was doubted for its feasibility by the chair of the business division based on the question of 'why Japan does not have this kind of design' (interviewee SD). Five years later, the first handle-free refrigerator launched in Japan; Taiwanese companies followed this trend a year later.

The above-mentioned case shows the conservative mindset of Taiwanese companies who were used to following Japanese design due to long-term technology dependency. As the market trends of household appliances in Taiwan generally followed Japan, the design trends of Japanese household appliances often dominated the styles of Taiwanese household appliances. A former designer from a large household appliance corporation once mentioned: 'at that time we were copycats of Toshiba; Toshiba had seven lines on the side, we copied it and changed the design to five lines, which was basically the same as theirs despite slight differences'. Another designer even confessed that: 'whoever counterfeited Japan faster looked the newest within Taiwan' (interviewee SA).

In the early stages, the design of Taiwanese household appliances was largely based on counterfeiting; outdated Japanese household appliances became the sources of Taiwanese companies' design and development (interviewee TA). The design of many Taiwanese household appliances directly copied outdated ones from collaborated Japanese companies, merely making partial changes to colors or the manual to fit the specialty of local markets. Therefore, instead of saying Japanese enterprises exported practical experiences of modern industrial design to Taiwan, it could be said that it was Taiwanese companies who paid sumptuous premiums through the form of joint ventures or technical cooperation to stop Japanese corporations from accusing Taiwan of counterfeiting their designs. In a predicament where production technologies were dependent on foreign capital, key components relied on imports, and design talents were few, Taiwan's industrial design progressed slowly.

ECONOMIC LIBERALIZATION - FACING THE WAVE OF ECONOMIC LIBERALIZATION

In the early 1980s, the pressure of free trade, conceived by international economic powers, hit many NICs who excelled in economic development, and exchange rate adjustment became one of the main measures to balance trade deficits. Following the appreciation of the Deutsch Mark and the

Japanese Yen, the exchange rate of the Taiwan Dollar against US Dollar kept on appreciating dramatically (as shown in Table 3). The production factor was no longer cheap, and it lacked attractiveness to foreign joint ventures or buyers. In 1984, Kuo-hwa Yu became the Premier of Taiwan, and he raised the suggestion of economic liberalization, which set the official economic policies for the 1980s.

On the contrary, along with the loosening of the cold war structure, China started to carry out economic reforms and open policies. Cheap labor and institutional encouragements attracted foreign capital to invest in China one after another, which either left Taiwan or re-organized in both China and Taiwan; they also generated a magnet effect on Taiwanese companies. When the international processing base began to face industrial transformation, industries that stayed in Taiwan began to face grim reality.

Table 3: Exchange rates of the Taiwan Dollar against the US Dollar, from 1980 to 1990

Exchange Rate (NTU/USD)	
Year	Rate (Unite: TWD)
1980	36.00
1981	36.84
1982	39.11
1983	40.06
1984	39.60
1985	39.85
1986	37.82
1987	31.77
1988	28.59
1989	26.40
1990	26.89

Source: Central Bank of Taiwan

'IN THE NAME OF CONSUMER' - THE LOOSENING OF SAFEGUARD POLICIES

Import controls and tariff barriers have always been the tools for governments to protect their local household appliance industry and to maintain competitive advantages. Policies such as the Tax Refund for Export (in 1955) and the Export Percentage Cap (in 1973) encouraged exports and prevented over-competition within local markets. Because customs and product taxes could be refunded for imported materials and components, companies' export costs were reduced. Compared with locally produced products that had product taxes imposed on them, it was said that imports subsidized exports. According to the (revised) Statute for the Encouragement of Investment in 1974, many export factories enjoyed duty free preferences. Consequently, Taiwanese household appliance manufacturers made excellent export records one after another.

At the same time, the government had long resorted to high import tariffs to protect local infant industries, and it severely restricted the imports of foreign household appliance until 1986. Under the

wave of the government's advocating for the purchase of local products, purchases of imported goods had the stigma of being extravagant, showing xenomania, and harming national industries. However, consumers who had better purchasing powers were more and more aware of their rights; household appliance brought in through smuggling and parallel imports could be regularly found. In 1984, the incident of TV manufacturers' excessive profits erupted. Household appliance with similar functions were much more expensive in Taiwan than in the US and Japan, therefore there was sentiment for condemnation among the general public. The target was not only pointed at whether there existed any cartel monopoly among corporations, but the justification of the government's safeguard policies were questioned by legislators and liberal scholars. In the same year, the Consumers' Foundation was established, targeting local consumer goods such as televisions and videotape player/recorders (VCR) that were of worse quality yet were more costly, demanding the lowering of customs and the relaxation of imports. Under this appeal, although companies had objections, they were silenced under the joint pressure from consumer groups, legislators and liberal scholars; the opinion of the government that used to favor the companies had started to reverse.

Under pressure from both international powers and local consumers, the government adapted to the wave of liberalization in the name of consumer after 1986, listing import restrictions, and adopting the measure to lower customs on imported household appliances on a yearly basis to reduce the impact on local manufacturers.

Household appliance manufacturers apparently suffered from the blow of trade liberalization; the market share of imported household appliances grew substantially, as shown in Table 4. Although the growth of imported goods and the decline of locally produced ones was due to the difference between (landed costs and market prices of) the tax base of the goods of the two, it indirectly proved the great extent to which local household appliance manufacturers were protected by the state. After Japanese and Korean household appliances flooded in, local businesses suffered from great losses, and their production lines were reduced almost by half.

Table 4: Share of imported household appliances in domestic markets

Product	Year	1987	1988	1989	1990
Color television		16%	49.2%	63.1%	63.3%
VCR		55.0%	55.9%	59.6%	54.0%
Air conditioner		8.1%	18.8%	29.5%	26.0%
Refrigerator		21.7%	45.8%	53.2%	54.2%
Washing machine		35.4%	57.0%	60.9%	60.9%

Source: Yeh, 1991.

Strictly speaking, lowering customs and lifting import bans were not the fatal factors that hit Taiwanese household appliance manufacturers. In the 1980s, household appliances had already become popular in Taiwanese families. According to research on the popularity of household appliances in Taiwan conducted by the Taiwan Power Company in September 1987, every 100 households owned 106.6 televisions, 96.2 refrigerators and 73.9 washing machines in October 1986 (Taiwan Power Company, 1987). For appliances, white goods such as refrigerators and washing machines are durable and long lasting, and their product replacement cycle is longer, therefore their growth within the domestic market was limited.

Because the domestic demand had been saturated, companies had to strive for overseas markets. However, Japanese companies often had deals written into technological transfer contracts, restricting exports or export regions of the products. For example, products could not be exported to regions or countries where the Japanese corporations had invested. Therefore, Taiwanese companies were restricted in the domestic market or some overseas regions from selling products and could not expand to the global market. At that time, most household appliances were products that had reached maturity, so the technical threshold for entering this industry was not high. Companies like Samsung and LG Electronics, which had just started operating in Korea, entered the international market, using the strategy of low-balling based on the economies of scale, which made Taiwanese companies' shares in overseas markets continue to decline.

In 1990, under the existing policy of joining the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT), industries such as the automobile and household appliance industries were affected by custom cuts; for the household appliance industry that was barely coping, the situation went from bad to worse.

The above-mentioned factors caused the household appliance industry in Taiwan to go from prosperity to decline, and their production began to stagnate. Through the evaluation of cost analysis, companies would rather let go of some items that were profitless and instead purchase them from other companies through OEM, hence formed a new wave of industrial integration and division of labor (interviewee SC). Facing this crucial moment, companies became active in developing new products, and industrial design was adopted by the household appliance industry in the hope that it could bring a chance of survival.

SEEKING SURVIVAL WITHIN THE CRACKS - 'JAPANESE BONE, AMERICAN SKIN' REFRIGERATORS MADE IN TAIWAN

Under the deregulation of imported household appliances, all kinds of stylish electrical household goods from around the world entered Taiwan, overwhelming Taiwan's household appliance market and causing a decline of the domestic

products' market share. Due to increased choices in consumer markets, it was assumed that the share of domestic products would be diluted. However, American refrigerators reached 60% of the total domestic share only two years after they began to be imported. In addition to tariff reductions that enabled American refrigerators to reduce product prices, this fact was contrary to the trend that Taiwan's consumer goods markets always followed Japanese consumer goods.

In 1968, the China Industrial Designers Association (CIDA) and three companies, including Tatung Co., Panasonic Taiwan, and Hsing-Rong, together held the 'forum on refrigerator observation'. They invited 100 women to give comments on 18 refrigerator models provided by the three companies, who then picked the most suitable model for the reference of manufacturers. These comments reflected the characteristics of refrigerators that housewives appreciated during that time: a median volume (200 to 250 liter), two doors, white, with no decorative patterns. Participants generally thought that domestic refrigerators could compete with foreign ones, and that there was no need to purchase from abroad (Chen, 1968). Ten years later, market research conducted by Kun-ming Tseng at Tatung Co. also found that in addition to Tatung, refrigerators manufactured by all the other companies did not exceed the maximum volume of 400 liters (Tseng, 1980). Thus, it could be rationally presumed that before the import bans on refrigerators were lifted, domestic copies of Japanese median refrigerators were still the mainstream in Taiwanese markets.

American refrigerators, which often exceeded a volume of 500 liters, were very different from the Japanese models that Taiwanese consumers were more familiar with. However, despite having several brands, the styles of imported American refrigerators all looked the same, which reflected the particular American life style. Kitchens in American families were mostly spacious, and there was room for a 500-liter refrigerator. It was just right for storing the bulk of the food purchased during the weekend. Although American refrigerators had noisy compressors, American houses were mostly made of wood, which absorbed noise, plus the kitchen and the bedrooms were often located on different floors; therefore noise was not agonizing. In addition, the yellow-colored surface suited the wooden interior and furniture of American homes, and the dry continental climate did not make the door of the refrigerator 'sweat'. From the perspectives of environment and climate, home space, and user habits, American refrigerators were against all Taiwanese consumers' life styles and real needs.

According to the above discussion, it is difficult to understand why American refrigerators were popular in Taiwan. Yet to the industry, and more importantly, imported American refrigerators started a wave of hot sales, seriously threatening

Japanese-style or sim-Japan refrigerators that had long occupied Taiwan's household appliance markets, bringing factory production lines nearly to a halt. To face this challenge, Taiwanese household appliance companies, which used to only design refrigerator handles and plates, had to re-establish production lines for new product specifications; otherwise they were faced with plant shutdowns. Industrial design became the last chance for refrigerator manufacturers, at a time when they were about to give up the market in Taiwan.

The huge changes in the refrigerator market left manufacturers at a loss about what to do. Even with technological support from the Japanese parent company, Panasonic Taiwan only came up with the responding strategy of beautifying the back side of the refrigerator's appearance, as only the interior was allowed to be redesigned by Taiwanese companies. Sampo Co., however, adopted more innovative and daring designs. The product merchandise and industrial design departments worked together to resist the suggestion of giving up the refrigerator business and resorting to imports; they were determined to do battle with American refrigerator manufacturers (interviewee SE). At that time, consumers generally felt the shortcomings of American refrigerators: noise, condensation, rust and poor planning of interior arrangements; therefore, Japanese refrigerators that were more delicate were catching up. As such, the counterattack of the local household appliance industry was not hopeless. However, they needed to find a way to create a 'refined large refrigerator' that overcame the shortcomings of American refrigerators while matching their large storage capacity.

Sampo Co. adopted design concepts from a Japanese handle-less refrigerator, in which the door was opened from the top. When viewed from the top, both sides of the refrigerator door were arc-shaped. The proportion of such a design was appropriate for small or median-sized refrigerators, in which the front side was narrower. However, once the volume of the refrigerator increased to 500 liters, the arc-shaped door sides created an illusion that the refrigerator was dented. Therefore, the design department made the whole door arc-shaped, which not only modified the visual effects but also highlighted the well-rounded image of large capacity. Sampo was also the first company to adopt mirror printing plate technology, which had just been developed in Japan. Mirror plates could be printed on multiple layers with multiple colors. Compared with traditional coatings, their surfaces were bright and shiny, had versatile colors and patterns, and had no rust issues, which largely enhanced the aesthetic requirements. Last but not least, the ultra slim design made the plates thinner. The whole appearance of the refrigerator looked smaller, yet it still had a large capacity. As for the interior, designers allocated easy access storage spaces according to local users' special diet habits, such as dumplings, Chinese medicine and cut fruit, which

further contrasted with the undue size of American refrigerators.

Combining the large storage capacity of American refrigerators, the delicacy of Japanese refrigerators, and domestic consumer needs, the Taiwanese refrigerator (as shown in Figure 3) was launched in 1989 and was instantly popular in the market. In just three months, the sales surged and made this a best selling product. Within half a year, other consumer appliance companies began requesting agreements for ODM cooperative production. In 1990 and 1991, orders averaged more than 20,000 units per year. As such, the market share of Sampo arc-shaped refrigerators and that of other brand names grew substantially in the market, which seriously impacted the sales of American refrigerators.

Figure 3: Sampo arc-shaped refrigerator

Source: Lee, 1996

For a long time, the household appliance industry in Taiwan occupied the lion's share of domestic markets under the tariff barriers set by the government. However, facing the change of policy direction towards import liberalization, the market share was declining substantially; companies were suffering from serious impacts and were almost brought to extinction. Yet, at this time, when American refrigerators had flooded the market and had a share as high as 36%, local refrigerator manufacturers brought about a complete turnabout, and this achievement has become legendary. Most importantly, industrial design went deep into the war of market competition, creating competitive advantages in the battle against American refrigerators and saving production lines that had nearly been brought to a halt.

CONCLUSION

In the process of Taiwan's modernization, the household appliance industry was a new comer in the domestic market. The government's safeguard policies contributed to the realization of profit maximization of local household appliance companies. When the domestic market reached saturation and the economic liberalization wave lifted restrictions on imports, the industry suffered from great impacts. This research reviewed the process of design development of local Taiwanese household appliance companies such as Tatung Co. and Sampo Co. after the Second World War. Based on the analytical framework of this research, the roles played by the government (and its industrial policies) and foreign capital (concerning technological input) during the process of local Taiwanese companies' design development are summarized as follows.

In the early stage after the Second World War, Taiwanese companies assembled radios and sold components for electrical appliances, which gradually became the early form of the household appliance industry. From the 1960s, the framework of the new international division of labor emerged, and traditional labor-intensive industries that were no longer profitable in industrialized countries. The low wage standards in Taiwan, plus factors such as household electrification and new television broadcasts, all attracted foreign capital from the US and Japan to Taiwan. After the technology was imported, Taiwanese companies started to manufacture many different types of electrical household goods, such as rice cookers, refrigerators, and televisions. However, through joint ventures and technology control, foreign capital only allowed Taiwanese companies to perform product assembly in their early stages of development, not to mention R&D.

Compared with foreign companies, in which foreign capital owns more than half of the shares, local household appliance manufacturers were more active in industrial design. In order to foster this local infant industry, the government restricted imports and raised tariffs. This economic structure formed by state policy intervention provided a good development basis for local Taiwanese companies that were in their early stages of product development and had low technology transfer levels. Based on the import of design concepts, plus through continuous promotions and demonstrations, a number of enterprises began to set up permanent design departments as well as the mechanisms for the operation of industrial design. Through interchanges and imitation, companies learned design operations in order to narrow the distance between products and local markets.

Beginning in the 1970s, local enterprises started to grow and mature. The development of design departments reached a certain scale, which could be flexibly embedded into the organization according to corporate targets, and could be incorporated into production processes in

accordance with the marketing and mechanical engineering departments. The household appliance industry could be called the cradle that nourishes industrial design in Taiwan. Among local household appliance companies, technological cooperation with Japanese capital on one hand provided Taiwan's industrial design with the shortcuts to dependent development, but on the other hand it still was in a dominant position by controlling key components and technology.

Under the protection of the government's safeguard policies and with support from foreign technology and capital, local household appliance companies gained a great proportion of shares in domestic markets. However, this situation suddenly changed in the mid-80s. At that time, global trade liberalization forced nation states to step back. Limitless global capital entered the market and restricted regional industrial spaces under the protection of tariffs. Sampo's arc-shaped refrigerator became the product in which local household appliance companies used industrial design to respond to international competition.

The above-mentioned descriptions can be further used to analyze the historical roles of the government, foreign capital, and corporations in the development of industrial design in local household appliance companies. In NICs after the Second World War, the government often actively intervened in the development of industries. In the early stages, measures such as import restrictions and tariff barriers were used to protect local infant industries. At the same time, expanded exports, plus the imports of foreign joint ventures in Taiwan, all contributed to technology spillover. These policies created the conditions for Taiwanese local household appliance companies to develop industrial design in the early stages. When these local enterprises wanted to raise their technical industrial design abilities, Japanese capital that owned partial shares played the role of technical advisor. Through channels including technological cooperation, observational lectures and human resource imports, the design experiences from the US and European countries that had been absorbed and transformed by Japanese corporations became the sources of industrial design for Taiwanese companies. However, obsolete, fragmented product drawings and market survey techniques were the starting point of industrial design in Taiwan. The energy that was incubated and accumulated during this period was able to respond to the impact of open markets in the 1980s, when the government gradually deregulated safeguard policies under the wave of international free trade and domestic consumer movements.

Overall, under government policies that persuaded farmers to transfer to the industrial sector in post-war Taiwan, the general public was incorporated into the production-consumption circle of industrial capitalism. Through technological cooperation with Japanese corporations, the Taiwanese household appliance industry became the

channel in which to mediate modernization, whereas industrial design played a behind the scenes role, indirectly pushing forward the modernization process in which Taiwanese society copied Japanese household electrification. Thereafter, Taiwan followed in the footsteps of the Japanese 'Three Sacred Treasures' [3] of the 1950s: black-and-white televisions, refrigerators and washing machines. As for how design development influences the society, however, this is another important issue in the study of design history.

NOTES

1. The concept of the developmental state was derived from some scholars' discussions on post-war East Asian countries, such as Japan, South Korea and Taiwan, as to how they directed the structural adjustment of industrial production in order to pursue economic development, as stated by Evans (1992). These discussions try to revise the oversimplified role of the state in theories of post-war development studies. Castells (2001) considers that East Asian nation states, facing challenges from the emerging civil society in the 1980s, were no longer able to gain their legitimacy to rule through authoritarian methods; especially in cases like Taiwan that ran 'flexible capitalism under inflexible state guidance', where past experiences are not sufficient to explain the history after the 1980s, when the state stepped back from market intervention under open and free trade in exchange for international recognition, and enterprises were forced to learn innovation and design automatically.

2. Kyochi Toyoguchi ran a design studio in Japan. His father, Katsuhei Toyoguchi, is famous for planning the 1970 Expo in Kyoto. Ting-shen Lin once wanted to invite Kyochi Toyoguchi to be the chief of the design department, but Toyoguchi suggested that it would be better to appoint a Taiwanese chief.

3. The Three Sacred Treasures of Japan (or the imperial Regalia of Japan) in Japanese mythology refer to the sword Kusanagi, the mirror Yata no kagami, and the jewel Yasakani no magatama. Legend has it that the three treasures were the symbols of the monarch during coronations. After the Second World War, Japan headed into a growing period of economic recovery, when household electrification gradually became popular. At that time if there were aerials on the roof, it meant that a household owned a television; therefore it symbolized the progress of household modernization.

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